

THE INFLUENCE OF WORD OF MOUTH (WOM), PRICE, AND NUTRITIONAL KNOWLEDGE ABOUT CALCIUM ON THE PURCHASE DECISION OF DAILY PRODUCTS IN ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract

This study aimed to analyze the effect of word of mouth, price, and knowledge of calcium on adolescents' decisions to purchase dairy products. One of the intakes needed in adolescence to prevent osteoporosis is milk, the main calcium source. The sample in this study was teenagers in high school in Jakarta, totaling 95 people according to random sampling, and analyzing the data using sperm rank correlation since the assumption of normality of the data was not met. The results showed a significant influence between word of mouth (WOM), price, and knowledge of calcium on adolescents' decision to purchase dairy products.

Keywords: Price, Knowledge, Purchase decision, Milk, Adolescent

I. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is marked by biological and psychological growth and development (Ningsih, 2018). Biologically, it is characterized by the growth and development of primary sex and secondary sex in which physical changes occur. While psychologically, it is characterized by uncertain or unstable attitudes, feelings, and emotions. To achieve optimal physical changes, adequate nutritional intake is needed (Hidayati & Farid, 2016).

Based on the 2019 RDA, the need for calcium in adolescents is 1200 mg/day. Research (Mardiyah & Fransiska, 2021) in the East Jakarta area showed that 85.8% of adolescents had low calcium intake, averaging 467.5 ± 317.1 mg or equivalent to 38.9% of the RDA, where this figure did not meet the calcium needs based on the RDA. Adequate calcium intake is essential for developing and maintaining peak bone mass during adolescence. Calcium deficiency in adolescence can lead to a reduction in the mass and hardness of bones that are being formed (Sudiarmanto & Sumarmi, 2020).

In adolescence, nutritional intake plays an important role in preventing chronic diseases in adulthood, such as the importance of adequate calcium intake to prevent osteoporosis (Limbong & Syahrul, 2015). Not consuming enough calcium can cause osteoporosis; the body does not get enough calcium from food, and the body will take it from the calcium bank found in the joints of the hands, feet, and other long bones. Meanwhile, if the lack of calcium in the

long term makes the body takes calcium from solid bones, this can cause bones to become porous and break easily, commonly called osteoporosis (Sriwahyuni, 2021).

Along with technological advances, especially in the livestock industry sector, dairy products are starting to be found on the market. Moreover, along with the times, more and more people are aware of the importance of fulfilling nutrition. They believe that if their nutritional needs are not met, it will be bad for their bodies, especially for children growing up (Papotot et al., 2021). Currently, many people are starting to consume milk every day. The level of milk purchases can influence milk consumption in the community. Knowledge of consumer nutrition will influence purchasing decisions. When consumers have more knowledge, they will be better at making decisions, more efficient and precise in processing information, and finding information better (Wahyuni, 2016).

According to Enre et al. (2020), purchase decisions are consumer decisions influenced by technology, politics, culture, economics, finance, products, prices, promotions, location, process, people, and physical evidence. It forms an attitude in consumers to process all information and draw conclusions in the form of responses, namely what products to buy. Kotler and Keller (2009) say that basic psychological processes play an important role in understanding consumers' purchasing decisions. Consumers go through five stages in decision-making: problem recognition, information seeking, and evaluation of alternatives, purchase decisions, and post-purchase behavior.

In the second stage of making purchasing decisions, there is Word of Mouth communication. Word of mouth is an action taken by consumers to other consumers in providing information about a product through word of mouth (Masturi & Hardini, 2019). This method is believed to be very effective in influencing purchasing decisions for a product because consumers tend to trust the people around them more who buy the product first when compared to advertising or other marketing (Qatrunnada, 2019). Sernovitz (2012) in Fenanda & Solekah, (2018) said that Word of Mouth has five important elements called The Five Ts. It consists of talkers, speakers or parties who disseminate information; topics, topics discussed products; tools, tools to facilitate the occurrence of Word of Mouth; taking part, company participation in the occurrence of Word of Mouth; tracking, a form of company supervision of the Word of Mouth that occurs.

In addition, price is also one of the main factors for consumers in considering their buying decisions (Hidayat, 2018). Price is the sum of all the values consumers exchange for the benefits of owning or using the product or service. Based on research results Halim (2021) shows that the price variable is known to have a t-count value of $2.336 > t\text{-table } 1.987$ with a significant value of $0.022 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that price has a significant effect on purchasing decisions of pure fresh cow's milk.

Pristiwati & Fikri (2021) found that Word of Mouth marketing communication influences purchasing decisions at the Etawa Mulia Jaya Goat Milk Business in Melati II Village, Perbaungan District. In this study, the Word Of Mouth Communication variable has a t value of $4.051 > t\text{ table } 1.988$ and a significant level of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the

Word Of Mouth Communication variable partially has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decisions. In line with Pamuleh et al. (2021), the results of the T-test (partial) for the word-of-mouth variable obtained a t count of $4.063 > 1.657$ with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the word of mouth variable has a significant effect on the purchasing decision variable.

A survey conducted on adolescents showed that teenagers rarely buy milk. 14.1% of respondents buy milk every day, 7.1% of respondents buy milk 4-6 times a week, and 78.6% buy milk 1-2 times a week. The average level of knowledge of calcium nutrition in adolescents is $< 60\%$, which means that knowledge of calcium nutrition in adolescents is in a low category, and 78% of adolescents stated that they often received recommendations about dairy products from other people. This study aimed to prove that word of mouth, knowledge, and price influence decision-making to buy dairy products.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Product Quality

Product quality is the ability of a product to meet consumer desires, including product durability, product reliability, ease of use, and other valuable attributes that are free from defects and damage (Wibisono, 2019). Habibah (2016) also revealed that product quality is the totality of goods and services related to consumer desires, which in terms of product excellence, are worthy of being sold according to customer expectations.

Product quality can determine consumer satisfaction after purchasing and using a product. So that based on consumer satisfaction with product quality will influence consumers to repurchase or not. Product quality is defined as a consumer's assessment of the attributes of a product that will satisfy their needs and benefit them (Anggar, 2018).

The quality of a product in the form of goods or services is determined through its dimensions. Dimensions of product quality perception include:

Performance, is related to the basic operating characteristics of a product.

Durability, which means how long or the age of the product in question lasts before the product must be replaced. The greater the frequency of consumer use of the product, the greater the power of the product.

Conformance to specifications, is the extent to which the basic characteristics of a product meet certain specifications from consumers or no defects are found in the product. In this case, the items have been paid for by consumers per consumers' expectations.

Features, are product characteristics designed to enhance product functions or increase consumer interest in the product.

Reliability, is the probability that the product will work satisfactorily or not within a certain period. The smaller the possible damage, the more reliable the product is (Tjiptono, 2008).

2. The Influence of Product Quality on Purchase Decisions

Usually, if the products offered by the company are of good quality, then consumers buy and consume directly, and the product exceeds the expectations of consumers, then it can be said that they are satisfied with the product. On the other hand, when they consume, they tend to be disappointed and switch to other products (Kurniawati et al., 2014). Hamidi & Prakoso (2018) revealed that Product quality positively influences consumer satisfaction, which means that the higher the product quality, the higher the consumer satisfaction.

3. Brand Image

Brand image is consumers' perceptions and preferences for brands, as reflected by various kinds of brand perceptions that exist in consumers' memories (Romadhoni, 2013). The brand image includes knowledge and belief in brand attributes (cognitive aspects), consequences of using the brand, and appropriate use situations, as well as evaluations, feelings, and emotions perceived with the brand (affective aspect) (Manik, 2021).

According to Romadhoni (2013), factors that affect brand image are:

- a) Advantages of brand association, is one of the factors forming a brand image, where the product excels in the competition.
- b) Strength of brand association, is how information enters consumers' memory and how the process persists as part of the brand image.
- c) The uniqueness of brand association to a brand. Therefore, a competitive advantage must be created that can be used as a reason for consumers to choose a particular brand.

4. The Influence of Brand Image on Purchase Decision

A distinct and unique brand image is important; as products become more complex and the market more crowded, consumers will rely more on brand image than actual brand attributes to make purchasing decisions (Evita, 2017). According to Manik (2021), Brand Image affects purchasing decisions for Toyota Yaris at PT Astra International Tbk-Toyota Auto 2000 Bumi Serpong Damai. It can be seen that a purchase decision will always follow an increase in Brand Image.

5. Price

Price is an element of the marketing mix that brings income or income for flexible companies, meaning that it can be changed quickly (Rizki, 2020). Price is money determined by the company in exchange for goods or services traded by a company to satisfy customer desires (Haryanto, 2013). Riyono & Budiharja (2016) also argues that price is an important element in a company where with the price, the company will get income for the sustainability of the company; price is also a tool that will be used for the process of exchanging goods or services by consumers. Price is also very relative. If a buyer has the opportunity to buy the same goods and services at a lower price, they will do so (Zulaicha & Irawati, 2016).

According to Kotler (2009) in Amilia (2017), price indicators are as follows:

Price affordability, an affordable price is what consumers expect before they make a purchase. Consumers will look for products whose prices they can afford.

Conformity of price with product quality, for certain products, consumers usually do not mind if they have to buy at relatively high prices as long as the quality of the product is good. However, consumers prefer products with low prices and good quality.

Price competitiveness, the company determines the selling price of a product by considering the price of the product sold by its competitors because the product can compete in the market.

Price compatibility with benefits Consumers sometimes ignore the price of a product but are more concerned with the benefits of the product.

6. The Impact of Price on Purchase Decision

Based on the results of the analysis of previous research on the effect of price on purchasing decisions of Batik Barong Gung Tulungagung in research Agatha (2018) shows that there is a significant effect of price on the purchasing decision of Batik Barong Gung Tulungagung. These results indicate that a better price determination will affect high purchasing decisions.

7. Word of Mouth (WOM)

Word of Mouth (WOM) or word of mouth communication is a communication process that provides recommendations individually or in groups for a product or service that aims to provide personal information (Aprodita, 2018). Wahdiana, (2018) argues that word of mouth is a communication made by consumers who have made purchases and tell their experiences about the product or service so that indirectly the consumer has promoted to other consumers through the conversation. Prasetiyo & Hidayat (2019) also said word of mouth is part of a promotional strategy in marketing activities that uses a satisfied person to person to increase product awareness and generate sales.

Several things can be used to determine Word of Mouth's success. Based on the opinion of Babin et al. (2005) in Wahdiana, (2018) stated to measure the Word of Mouth using several indicators as follows:

- a) Talking, the ability of a person to speak positive things about product quality to others. Consumers expect maximum satisfaction and have interesting material to discuss with others.
- b) Recommend, consumers want products that can satisfy and have advantages compared to others, so they can be recommended.
- c) Push, encourages friends or relatives to make transactions for products and services. Consumers want attractive feedback when influencing others to use the product or service that has been announced.

8. Effect of Word of Mouth on Purchase Decision

Research by Masturi & Hardini, (2019) revealed that word of mouth positively and significantly affects purchasing decisions for Hokido karate-gi in five Dojos in the DKI Jakarta area. That is, the higher the positive word of mouth for a product, the higher the level of

purchasing decisions. This is because stories about a person's good experience in using a product can influence people who listen to the experience to make purchasing decisions for the product.

In line with research Rupayana et al. (2021) shows that word of mouth (WOM) has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. This shows that better word of mouth (WOM) in the consumer environment will increase purchasing decisions on the product.

9. Calcium Nutrition Knowledge

Knowledge results from knowing after people have sensed a certain object (Wardani & Prianggajati, 2015). Sensing occurs through the five human senses, namely: the senses of sight, hearing, smell, taste, and touch. Most human knowledge is obtained through eyes and ears (Notoatmodjo, 2007 in ayu, 2020). Knowledge of calcium, especially regarding calcium sources, is the first step to increasing calcium intake because adolescents with insufficient calcium still need information about calcium sources (Rachmiaty, 2019). Knowledge of consumer nutrition will influence purchasing decisions. Consumers with more knowledge will be better at making decisions, more efficient and precise in processing information, and find information better (Wahyuni, 2016).

10. Purchase Decision

The purchase decision is a consumer's decision to buy a product after thinking about whether or not to buy the product by considering the information that he knows about the reality of the product after he has witnessed it (Triyanto, 2014). Meanwhile, according to Harahap, (2017), purchasing is the process of making decisions from several alternatives to purchase a product. Zulaicha & Irawati, (2016) also argues that the purchase decision is an alternative behavior selection activity from two or more alternatives that are carried out by each individual to choose the appropriate alternative. Prayoga & Rachman, (2020) also expressed the same opinion; the purchase decision is a decision-making action consisting of two choices or more by analyzing a need and desire first, then searching for information and an assessment that is assessed based on customer satisfaction.

12. Factors Influencing Purchase Decisions

Purchase decisions are influenced by several factors, including:

a. Price

Based on the results of the analysis of previous research on the effect of price on purchasing decisions of Batik Barong Gung Tulungagung in research Agatha, (2018) shows that there is a significant effect of price on the purchasing decision of Batik Barong Gung Tulungagung. These results indicate that a better price determination will affect high purchasing decisions.

b. Brand Image

A distinct and unique brand image is important as products become more complex and the market more crowded; consumers will rely more on brand image than actual brand attributes to make purchasing decisions (Evita, 2017). Based on research Manik, (2021), the Brand Image

affects purchasing decisions for Toyota Yaris at PT Astra International Tbk-Toyota Auto 2000 Bumi Serpong Damai. It can be seen that a purchase decision will always follow an increase in Brand Image.

c. Product Quality

Usually, if the product offered by the company is of good quality, then consumers buy and consume it directly, and the product exceeds the expectations of consumers, then it can be said that they are satisfied with the product. On the other hand, when they consume, they tend to be disappointed and switch to other products (Kurniawati et al., 2014). In the research of Hamidi & Prakoso, (2018), Product quality directly has a positive influence on consumer satisfaction, which means that the higher the product quality, the higher the consumer satisfaction.

d. Knowledge of nutrition

Consumer knowledge will influence purchasing decisions. When consumers have more knowledge, they will be better at making decisions, will be more efficient and more precise in processing information, and will be able to find information better (Wahyuni, 2016)

e. Word of Mouth

Masturi & Hardini, (2019) revealed that word of mouth has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions for the Hokido brand karate-gi in five Dojos in the DKI Jakarta area. That is, the higher the positive word of mouth for a product, the higher the level of purchasing decisions. This is because stories about a person's good experience in using a product can influence people who listen to the experience to make purchasing decisions for the product. In line with research Rupayana et al., (2021) show that electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. This shows that better electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) in the consumer environment will increase purchasing decisions on OPPO brand smartphone products in Denpasar city.

III. METHOD

The design of this study was cross-sectional. The independent variables were the word of mouth, price, and nutritional knowledge about calcium, while the dependent variable was purchasing decisions. The population in this study were all adolescent high school students (SMA 48 Jakarta), totaling 568 students. After calculations using the Slovin formula (Adiputra, 2021) obtained a sample of 85 teenage students with an addition of 10% to anticipate dropout samples so that the number of samples became 95 respondents.

To determine the possibility of a significant relationship between the independent and dependent variables (Savitri, 2015). The bivariate analysis in this study was to determine the effect of the word of mouth, price, and knowledge of calcium nutrition on purchasing decisions of dairy products. This test was carried out using the Spearman Rank correlation test because the assumption of normality of the data was not met.

Here is the Spearman Rank correlation test formula:

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6\sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Note:

ρ = Spearman Rank correlation value

d^2 = The difference between each pair of ranks

N = Number of rank pairs for spearman

Through the Spearman Rank correlation test, the p-value would be obtained, where in this study, the significance level (α) = 0.05 was used, i.e., if the p-value was 0.05, it means a significant effect between the independent variable and the dependent variable, and if the p-value was > 0.05 means no significant effect between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Then to determine the strength of the relationship between variables was divided into 4, namely:

$r = 0.00 - 0.25$ = There is no relationship or weak relationship

$r = 0.26 - 0.50$ = Medium relationship

$r = 0.51 - 0.75$ = Strong relationship

$r = 0.86 - 1.00$ = Very strong relationship

Figure 1: Research Model Conceptual

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Description of Respondents' Characteristics

Characteristics of respondents in adolescents can be seen in Table 1

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents' Characteristics

Characteristics		N	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	43	45.5 %
	Female	52	54.7 %
Age	15 y.o	33	34.7 %
	16 y.o	40	42.1 %
	17 y.o	22	23.2 %

* Source: Data processed by researchers from SPSS version 16.0 (2022)

Based on table 1, it can be seen that there were more female respondents, about 54.7%, while male respondents were 45.5%. The age shows that respondents aged 16 years were 42.1%, while respondents aged 15 years were 34%, and respondents aged 17 years were 23.2%.

2. Word of Mouth (WOM) Overview

The Word of Mouth analysis results in adolescents can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Results of Word of Mouth Variable Analysis in Adolescents

Variable	Mean ± SD	Min - Max	95% CI
Word of Mouth	35.7 ± 7.9	14-52	34.1 – 37.3

* Source: Data processed by researchers from SPSS version 16.0 (2022)

Based on the analysis results, the average word-of-mouth score was 35.7, with a standard deviation of 7.9. From the results of the interval estimation, it can be assumed that 95% believed that the average word-of-mouth questionnaire score was 34.1 – 37.3.

3. Price Overview

The results of the price analysis in adolescents can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3: Results of Price Variable Analysis in Adolescents

Variable	Mean ± SD	Min - Max	95% CI
Price	16.3 ± 2.1	11 – 20	15.9 – 16.7

* Source: Data processed by researchers from SPSS version 16.0 (2022)

Based on the analysis results, the average score on the price questionnaire was 16.3, with a standard deviation of 2.1. From the results of the interval estimation, it can be assumed that 95% believed that the average score on the price questionnaire was 15.9 – 16.7.

4. Overview of Nutrition Knowledge about Calcium

The results of the analysis of nutrition knowledge about calcium in adolescents can be seen in table 4.

Table 4: Results of Variable Analysis of Nutrition Knowledge about Calcium in Adolescents

Variable	Mean ± SD	Min - Max	95% CI
Nutrition knowledge about calcium	6.7 ± 1.5	2 – 9	6.3 – 7.0

* Source: Data processed by researchers from SPSS version 16.0 (2022)

Based on the analysis, the average nutritional knowledge score about calcium was 6.7, with a standard deviation of 1.5. From the results of the interval estimation, it can be assumed that 95% believed that the average score on the calcium nutrition knowledge questionnaire was 6.3 – 7.0.

5. Overview of Dairy Product Purchase Decisions

The analysis results of the decision to purchase dairy products in adolescents can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Results of Analysis of Variables for Decision to Purchase Dairy Products in Adolescents

Variable	Mean ± SD	Min - Max	95% CI
Purchase decision	20.1 ± 3.4	9 – 25	19.4 – 20.8

* Source: Data processed by researchers from SPSS version 16.0 (2022)

Based on the analysis, the average nutritional knowledge score about purchase dairy product was 20.1, with a standard deviation of 3.4. From the results of the interval estimation, it can be assumed that 95% believed that the average score on the purchase dairy product questionnaire was 19.4– 20.8.

6. Analysis of the Effect of Word of Mouth on Decisions to Purchase Dairy Products in Adolescents

The results of the analysis of the influence of word of mouth on purchasing decisions of dairy products in adolescents showed in Table 6.

Table 6: Results of Analysis of the Effect of Word of Mouth on Decisions to Purchase Dairy Products in Adolescents

Dairy Product Purchase Decision		
Word of Mouth	ρ (r)	0.401
	P value	0.000
	N	95

* Source: Data processed by researchers from SPSS version 16.0 (2022)

Based on Table 5, it can be seen that there was a significant influence between Word of Mouth and the decision to purchase dairy products, with a p-value of 0.000 and a value of r = 0.401, which means the strength of the relationship was moderate. A study by Pristiwati & Fikri, (2021) found The Word Of Mouth communication variable has a significant level of 0.000 <0.05, which means that the Word Of Mouth Communication variable has a significant effect

on purchasing decisions in the goat milk business. This research is supported by research Pamuleh et al., (2021), that the results of the T-test (partial) for the word-of-mouth variable obtained a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$, meaning that the word-of-mouth variable has a significant effect on the product purchase decision variable.

The higher the positive word of mouth for a product, the higher the level of purchasing decisions for the product. This is because stories about a person's good experience in using a product can influence people who listen to the experience to make purchasing decisions for the product.

7. Analysis of the Effect of Price on Decision to Purchase Dairy Products in Adolescents

The results of the bivariate analysis of the effect of price on purchasing decisions of dairy products in adolescents can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7: Results of Bivariate Analysis of the Effect of Price on Decision to Purchase Dairy Products in Adolescents

Dairy Product Purchase Decision		
Price	ρ (r)	0.483
	P value	0.000
	N	95

* Source: Data processed by researchers from SPSS version 16.0 (2022)

Based on table 7, it can be seen that there was a significant influence between price and the decision to purchase dairy products with a p-value of 0.000 and a value of $r = 0.483$, which means the strength of the relationship was moderate. A study by Agatha (2018) shows a p-value of 0.000, which is smaller than $= 0.05$, so in this study, it can be assumed that price significantly affects purchasing decisions. Research Halim supports this research; the study obtained a significant value of $0.022 < 0.05$, meaning that the price significantly affects purchasing decisions for pure fresh cow's milk. The better the price determination, the higher the purchase decision will be.

8. Analysis of the Effect of Knowledge about Calcium on Decisions to Purchase Dairy Products in Adolescents

The analysis of the influence of knowledge about calcium on purchasing decisions of dairy products in adolescents can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8: Results of Analysis of the Effect of Knowledge of Calcium on Decisions to Purchase Dairy Products in Adolescents

Dairy Product Purchase Decision		
Calcium Nutrition Knowledge	ρ (r)	0.306
	P value	0.003
	N	95

* Source: Data processed by researchers from SPSS version 16.0 (2022)

Based on Table 8, it can be seen that there was a significant influence between price and the decision to purchase dairy products with a p-value of 0.003 and a value of $r = 0.306$, which means the strength of the relationship was moderate. Knowledge of calcium, especially regarding calcium sources, is the first step to increasing calcium intake because adolescents with insufficient calcium still need information about calcium sources (Rachmiaty, 2019). The results of this study indicate that the value of $p = 0.003$, so the value of $p > 0.05$ means a significant influence between knowledge of calcium nutrition and purchasing decisions of dairy products and obtained the value of $r = 0.306$, which means the strength of the relationship is. So it can be concluded that the variable knowledge of calcium nutrition affects purchasing decisions of dairy products in adolescents.

This research is supported by research Endah & Handaruwati, (2022), the results of the t-test value $t\text{-count } 2.639 > t\text{-table } 1.98$ with a significant value of 0.004, meaning that there is a significant influence between knowledge and purchasing decisions.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the study results, it is known that word of mouth (WOM) and price jointly affect the decision to purchase dairy products, so the dairy company pays attention to price and word of mouth to improve product purchasing decisions. The knowledge variable about calcium affects the decision to purchase dairy products, so the school should assist in providing education about calcium nutrition because the higher the purchase decision, the higher the level of milk consumption.

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